

Implementation of Police-reform Programme and Performance of Kenyan Police-Service

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Abstract

The present study examined the influence of the implementation police-reform programme on performance of Kenyan police-service. The specific objectives were to determine the influence of management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform and police-training on performance of Kenyan police-service in Kenya. The study was founded on institutional theory and reinforcement theory. Descriptive survey utilizing cross-sectional approach was adopted. The target population was 1,396 police-officers consisting of police inspectors, police sergeants and constables and corporals in the regional police headquarters in Eastern Kenya. Yamane`s formula was used to generate 316 sample size. Proportionate stratified random sampling was then used to distribute the respondents across the 3 sub-populations. Data was collected using structured-questionnaires and unstructured-interview schedules. Reliability of the research instrument was tested using split-half method at 0.7 Cronbach`s alpha coefficient (for $\alpha = 0.81$). Quantitative data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Pearson correlation technique was used to determine the relationships between variables. Regression analysis was used to test the fitness of the research model in predicting performance of Kenyan police-service. Hypothesis was tested using F-test at 95% confidence interval. Qualitative data was analyzed using content analysis. Inferential statistics indicated that the strength of influence of the implementation of police-reform programme on performance of Kenyan police-service decreased in the following order police-training ($r=0.85$), structural-reform (0.78), management-reform ($r=0.60$) and leadership-reform ($r=0.30$). The research model was deemed fit since it predicted 84% variation in the performance of Kenyan police-service (for $R^2=0.84$). It was concluded that implementation of police-reform programme

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is a critical influencer of the performance of Kenyan police-service. Government should review the police reform agenda and put more efforts on police training in order to enhance police performance. Also, there is need to strengthen and integrate leadership and management of police service through relevant policy interventions. Project managers can utilize the findings by adopting adaptive approaches in the coordination and management of future projects in order to render more effective and sustainable impacts. Based on the limitations of the study, future researches can explore the phenomenon in different project contexts for more generalizable findings.

Keywords: Implementation of police-reform programme, police-training, structural-reform, management-reform, leadership-reform, performance of Kenyan police-service,

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Introduction

Globally, security is very elusive. This is due to the complexities of the environment in which security is built. As a result, the contemporary policing is facing dynamic challenges that continue to pose safety and security (Balve and Spang, 2017). For instance, the continued proliferation of nuclear arms, international terrorism, cyber security, armed conflict and other non-military factors like economic imbalances, pollution and even food shortages are some of the threats that continue to pose threats to global security and peace (Izumikawa, 2020). As a result, global leaders are calling for resilience in peacebuilding and sustaining peace. This was stressed by the president of the Republic of Kenya when he chaired United Nations Security Council meeting held on 12th October, 2021 at the United Nations headquarters in New York stressed on the need to embrace diversity in conflict situation while respecting and strengthening the structures that maintain peace and security (United Nations News, 2021). It follows that any hindrance to the realization of national, regional and global security, peace and stability is a concern of every state.

Whether contextually or historically, security challenges are compelling police organizations to redefine their strategies in strengthening their security apparatus, cooperation strategies and reform in security institutions in order to safeguard masses and property. For example, there is the Global security body called United Nations Security Council, Europe and USA has military alliance called Northern Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), Russia and China have Sino-Russia military cooperation, and Africa has the peace and security council in charge of enforcing security decisions on behalf of member states. In pursuit of security, the choice of a security strategy is invariably based on the geographical and contextual settings of a county and characteristics of a situation. For this reason, it is important to address security issues from normative perspectives while doing critical as well as self-examination with regard to the diverse viewpoints (Hagmann, 2021).

In United States of America, there is widespread demand to overhaul the entire policing and integrate local policing due to the widespread violence (Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime GIATOC, 2020). Amongst the proposed reform remedies in USA includes: strengthening the resilience of the locals, demilitarizing fighting of crime, reduction of vulnerability, defunding the criminal elites, abolishing umbrella protection of politicians and use of intelligence. In European countries, police practice and reforms are shifting towards enhancing organization of policing systems through integration of local communities with national and international police organizations and policymakers so as to enhance citizen reporting, information monitoring, mobile value transfer so as to support planning, responding and dissemination of real time security information (European Union EU, 2020). In Canada, the clamour for police reform is taking a programme approach whereby the government is implementing policing programmes so as to assist delivery of appropriate services to the local communities (Breutigam and Fortier, 2019). In the Asian countries, police reform is taking shape through institutional and legal reforms as guided by the international standards and norms good practice (Kocak, 2018). This is being done to promote service delivery and national ownership of policing. Waruiru and Rugami (2017) support that police-reforms and cultural change have significant contribution to the police-service delivery and patriotism. In Russia, the interventions include comprehensive training and modernization of policing so as to ensure professionalism (McCarthy, 2018).

African peace security council is the top organ mandated to implement security decisions on behalf of African Union (Nagar and Nganje, 2016). For example, following increased terrorism and insurgence activities that posed serious threat to regional peace and stability, African Union Mission in Somalia was created in 2007 to help to promote peace and stabilization of the Somalia government. The general security in African states is faced by challenges ranging from corruption, homicides, serious violence, insurgencies and terrorism. In response, African states are quickly adopting innovative reform strategies to curb crime and promote rule of law and human rights (Etannibi et al., 2018). In Zimbabwe for example, police reform agenda is going beyond police institutions to a culture of shared responsibilities between the community, police and other security actors like customs officials. Specific interventions in Zimbabwe includes internal and external police oversight mechanisms, collaboration with judiciary and prosecuting agencies (Manayiti, 2017).

The regional strategic plan (2019-2028) for the East African community (EAC) recognizes the elusive nature of conflicts and political insecurity the region. This led to establishment of interstate security council to oversee the implementation of the framework of cooperation and coordination of security programmes. Still in the EAC, the member states have developed common standards for policing promoting which includes: public-police confidence, human rights, police-community relationship and good police working condition (APCOF African Policing Civilian Oversight Forum APCOF, 2010). Nonetheless, there lacks collective institutional framework for cascading civilian oversight and operationalizing police reform.

In Kenya, the traditional ways of controlling crime mainly through reactive practices has been criticized by citizens due to lack of effectiveness (Community Policing Information Booklet, 2017). The journey of police reform kicked off in 2003 due to the increased demand for efficient, effective, accountable and responsive Kenyan police-service (Republic of Kenya, 2015). Previous reforms in police-service are documented in the police reform strategy of 2011-2014. The reform aims at: a) developing appropriate police governing laws and policies, b) building sustainable policing structures, c) enhancing police professionalism and accountability, d) increasing operational capacities of police and e) better coordination of policing activities (Government of Kenya, 2012). However, the first phase of police reform was critiqued over low performance as the reforms took longer time than expected to manifest (Kivoi, 2021). As a result, police-reform programme 2015-2018 was conceived in line with the constitutional of Kenya 2010 to modernize and transform police towards realization of sustainable peace and security per the Vision 2030 (Republic of Kenya, 2015). But the benefits of the programme are yet to be enjoyed per citizens` expectation.

Statement of the Problem

Residents of Eastern region of Kenya have raised concerns over increasing incidences of crimes and insecurity notwithstanding the implementation of police-reform programme (Kirui, 2021; Githinji, 2019). In 2019, Eastern Region reported 9,555 and a crime index of 329 (Government of Kenya, 2019). This is despite the implementation of police-reform programme. In the regional police headquarters in Kenya, the performance of police-service is negatively hampered by inadequate budget constraints, poor performance framework, ineffective coordination due to the extended span of control, poor police cooperation, lack of clarity of police mandates, staff turnover, inadequate work tools and inadequate police welfare which have continued to dysfunction the implementation the programme (Tilley and Sidebottom, 2017; IPOA, 2019). Other constraints relate to structural inflexibility which limit

innovative dissemination of police-service. In addition, there are issues related to police capacity, quality of work facilities and low public awareness regarding the objectives of police-reform (KNCHR and CHRP, 2019). There are allegations that middle level police-officers in eastern region are hindering performance of police due to resentment by junior officers over loss of independence (Tilley and Sidebottom, 2017). These challenges have hampered management decisions during the policing activities leading to poor service delivery and loss of public confidence as indicated by sustained police brutality (Human Rights Watch, 2021). Owing to the changing organizational priorities, implementation of police-reform programme has failed to deliver on key outputs like transparency, teamwork, mobility, responsiveness, police-community leading to poor satisfaction among the public (UNODC, 2018). It implies that the performance of Kenyan police-service is at high risk owing to the structural and contextual challenges. Questions arise on why the performance of police service is below the expected levels despite the robust police-reform programme.

A study by Waruiru and Rugami (2017) on the contribution of police-reform programmes to polices service delivery blames poor police performance to the disconnect between the priority areas and practicability in meeting the policing needs Other studies have demonstrated that empowering police-officers through training contributes to the performance of police reform programme (Mumanthi and Gachunga, 2014). Specifically, on-the-job training enhances productivity and performance of police (Maina and Waithaka, 2017). Also, structural flexibility is claimed to have direct influence on implementation of projects (Michira and Anyieni, 2018; Nahod and Radujkovic, 2018). However, management-reform is said to moderates the interplay of leadership-project success (Ali, Li, Khan et al., 2020). Ahmed (2016) has provided insightful knowledge on the enablers of project and programme performance in Pakistan. However, the findings cannot be generalized across all other projects and programmes due to contextual diversities. Guided by the reform areas of the police-reform programme and supported by the existing empirical literature, the present study examined how police-reform programme influence the performance of Kenyan police-service in Kenya. The present study was motivated by the results from a report by IPOA (2019) which suggested that only 63.3% of police-officers and 61% of the public have confidence that police are effectively discharging their duties. This is despite the implementation of police-reform programme.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To determine the influence of management-reform on performance of Kenyan police-service for the case of regional police headquarters, Kenya.
- ii. To assess the influence of structural-reform on performance of Kenyan police-service for the case of regional police headquarters, Kenya.
- iii. To examine the influence of leadership-reform on performance of Kenyan police-service for the case of regional police headquarters, Kenya.
- iv. To establish the influence of police-training on performance of Kenyan police-service for the case of regional police headquarters, Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significance influence of implementation of the police-reform programme on performance Kenyan police-service in Kenya.

Theoretical Framework

Institutional theory was advanced by Meyer, Powell, DiMaggio and Rowan in 1970s to advance the thinking of organization's tendency to achieve its strategic interests while adapting and conforming to the existing pressures (Amenta and Ramsey, 2009). Built on the concept of legitimacy other than efficiency and/ or effectiveness, institutional theory states that institutions exist in a volatile environment that constantly pressure and influence the structural, organizational, management and operational processes (Doug and Scott, 2004). institutional theory was used to explain the contribution of police-reform programme (management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform and police-training) help police as an institution to adapt to the changing need in order for police-service to perform better.

Reinforcement theory was developed by Skinner (1948) to advance the paradigm that behaviors are shaped by the consequences. Reinforcement theory is based on the law of effects of actions taken. Organizations exist in very elusive internal and external environments which constantly affect the way they operate. Most effective organizations are designed to effectively and positively motivate the internal environment while sparingly adapting to the external agents of change. Reinforcement theory was used to explain how the organization of police-reform programme (management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform, police-training) reinforce performance of Kenyan police-service.

Literature Review

Empirical studies were reviewed pursuant to the research variables. Methodological, theoretical, conceptual, contextual and environmental knowledge-gaps were identified and summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Knowledge-gaps

Variables	Authors	Study focus	Study Findings	Knowledge-gap
Management-reform and performance	Ali, Li, Khan et al. (2020)	management-reform, leadership-project success in China	Management-reform moderates leadership and project success	Ignored linear relationship. Contextually limited to China
	Ahmed (2016)	Top management-reform and performance of public sector projects in Pakistan	Top management-reform influences project performance	Relied on numerical data only. Conceptual limitation of top-management reform
Structural-reform and performance	Zeller (2021)	Organizational structure and performance of technological projects in USA	Organizational structures affects performance of projects	Relied on secondary data thus lowering internal validity for drawing conclusions
	Michira and Anyieni (2018)	Organization structure and implementation of projects in SACCO in Kenya	Organizational structure influences performance of projects	The findings were not anchored on any theoretical framework thus lowering construct validity
Leadership-	Eltayeb,	Leadership style	Transformational	Conceptually, the study

reform on performance	Ahmad and Al-Hajri (2019). Renzi (2020)	and performance in Saudi Arabia	project in project performance	leadership contributed to in project performance	was limited to leadership styles thus negating leadership practices
		Leadership styles and project implementation in USA		Leadership style has variant influence on performance	The conclusions were based on secondary data thus lowering content validity
Police-training and performance	Maina and Waithaka (2017). Kingoo and Njoroge (2019)	Training and performance of the Kenyan Police-service	Training and performance in national Kenyan police-service	Training has positive influence on performance	A sample of 85 fell below the minimum of 104 recommended for correlational analysis
		Training intervention and performance in national Kenyan police-service		Training has significant influence on performance of police	The indicators of training were inadequate thus limiting explanation of the variable

Conceptual Framework

The conceptualization of the study is shown in Figure 1.

Predictor Variable

(Implementation of Police-reform Programme)

- Management Reform**
 - Goal-setting
 - Interpersonal relations,
 - Problem solving
- Structural Reform**
 - Flexibility
 - Delegation
 - Employee focus
- Leadership Reform**
 - Participation
 - Motivation
 - Inspiration
- Police Training**
 - Training type
 - Training content
 - Frequency of training

Outcome Variable

(Performance of Kenyan Police Service)

- Performance of police-service in Kenya**
 - Transparency levels
 - Teamwork levels
 - Mobility levels
 - Responsiveness
 - Police-community relations
 - Satisfaction levels

- Moderating Variable**
 - Work environment
 - Police Welfare
 - Terms of police-service

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

A descriptive survey research with cross-sectional approach was used. The study targeted a population 1,396 police-officers including police inspectors, police sergeants and constables and corporals at the regional police headquarters in Eastern Kenya. A sample size of 316 was arrived at using Yamane's formula. Respondents were distributed across the sub-populations using proportionate stratified random sampling. While structured questionnaires were used to obtain quantitative data from respondents, qualitative data was obtained using unstructured-interviews. Reliability of the instrument was established by split-half method at 0.7 Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Quantitative data was analyzed through statistical packages for social sciences version 26 upon which descriptive and inferential statistics were generated. Pearson correlation Method was used to determine the relationships between predictor and outcome variables. regression analysis was used to test the fitness of the research model in predicting performance of Kenyan police-service. Hypothesis was tested using F-test at 95% confidence interval. Qualitative data was analyzed through coding, generation of themes and summarization. The research model was as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Whereby: Y is performance of Kenyan police-service, X_1 is management-reform, X_2 is structural-reform, X_3 is leadership-reform, X_4 is police-training, β_0 is constant, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ are coefficients for each variable and ε is error term.

Results

Table 2 presents the findings from correlational analysis

Table 2: Relationship Between Implementation of Police-reform Programme and Performance of Kenyan Police-service in Kenya

		Performance of Kenyan police-service	Management-reform	Structural-reform	Leadership-reform	Police-training
Performance of Kenyan police-service	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1				
	n	257				
Management-reform	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.60**	1			
	n	257	257			
Structural-reform	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.78**	0.47**	1		
	n	257	257	257		
Leadership-reform	Pearson Correlation	0.30**	0.30**	0.36**	1	

	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00		
	n	257	257	257	257	
	Pearson Correlation	0.85**	0.47**	0.66**	0.29**	1
Police-training	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	
	n	257	257	257	257	257

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the strongest relationship between implementation of police-reform programme and performance of Kenyan police-service was linked to police-training (for r=0.85) followed by structural-reform (for r=0.78) and then management-reform (for r=0.60) and finally leadership-reform (for r=0.30).

Performance of Kenyan Police-service was then regressed against implementation of police-reform programme. Table 3 presents the summary of the findings.

Table 3: Regression of the Implementation of Police-reform Programme and Performance of Kenyan Police-service in Kenya.

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics R ² Change	Change Statistics F Change	Change Statistics df1	Change Statistics df2	Sig. Change
1	0.92 ^a	0.84	0.84	0.12	0.84	328	4	252	0.00

a. Predictors:(Constant), management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform, police-training

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.61	4	4.90	328	0.00 ^b
	Residual	3.77	252	0.02		
	Total	23.38	256			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Kenyan police-service

b. Predictors: (Constant), management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform, police-training

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.39	0.14		0.28	0.78
	Management-reform	0.21	0.03	0.20	6.68	0.00
	Structural-reform	0.34	0.03	0.36	10.10	0.00
	Leadership-reform	-0.06	0.03	-0.06	-2.08	0.04
	Police-training	0.52	0.03	0.54	15.52	0.00

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Kenyan Police-service

The null hypothesis stated that:

H₀: There is no significance influence of implementation of police-reform programme on performance Kenyan police-service

From the model summary in Table 3, the null hypothesis was rejected as there was adequate evidence to conclude that implementation of police-reform programme has significant relationship performance of Kenyan police-service (for R=0.92).

Still, the model summary in Table 3 indicates that management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform and police-training accounted for 84% in the variation of performance of Kenyan police-service (for R²=0.84). The outstanding 16% was explained by other factors.

According to the ANOVA data in Table 3, for p=0.000<0.05 and F=328, it confirms that the model was fit in forecasting the performance of Kenyan police-service. Hence, the model was considered significant for predicting performance of Kenyan police-service.

The coefficient data in Table 3 shows that the constant for performance of Kenyan police-service was 0.39. Holding other factors constant, a unit change in management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform and police-training would trigger a change in the performance of Kenyan police-service the magnitudes of 0.20, 0.36, -0.06 and 0.54 respectively. The simplified research model becomes:

$$Y = 0.39 + 0.20X_1 + 0.36X_2 - 0.06X_3 + 0.54X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Whereby, Y= Performance of Kenyan police-service in regional police headquarters, Kenya, X₁= Management-reform, X₂= Structural-reform, X₃= Leadership-reform, X₄= Police-training, β₀ is a constant term, while β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ are coefficients of determination for X₁, X₂, X₃, X₄ accordingly and ε is the error term.

Discussion

The results showed that all variables of implementation of police-reform programme (management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform, police training) had significant influence on the performance of policer-service in Kenya. The finding is supported by past empirical studies, institutional theory and reinforcement theories. For instance, management-reform regulates the leadership in organization leading to more successful project (Ali, Li, Khan et al., 2020). Ahmed (2016) stresses on the importance of reform in the top-management in increasing performance. Management improves performance of workers through goal setting, interpersonal relations, clarifying of goals and problem-solving (Klein et al., 2019). Managers who clarify and define goals to workers help in setting objectives and reasonable tasks (PMI., 2021). In the present study, management-reform enhanced police-service though better goal setting, interpersonal relations and problem solving.

Effective organization structures outline the flow of tasks and activities in a coordinated order leading to greater achievement of the set goals (Nahod and Radujkovic, 2018). Reformed structures are flexible, lean, adequate delegation, clear line of authority, emphasis on staff in order to deliver. Simple structures guarantee efficient in the utilization of economic resources when responding to the changing environment for project to deliver. Such structures allow for ease communicating and coordinating of project operations in order to deliver (Michira and Anyieni, 2018). This leads to high performing organizations (Zeller,

2021). Michira and Anyieni (2018) support that innovative organizational structures have significant influence on the implementation of strategic plan projects. Other empirical findings by Hinings and Greenwood (2017), Zeller (2018), Michira and Anyieni (2018), Nahod and Radujkovic (2018), Zeller (2021) and Michira and Anyieni (2018) support that reformed structures contribute to the performance of an organization. Institutional theory and reinforcement theory support that flexible structures enhance innovation in navigation towards realization of organization goals. Therefore, structural-reform is a critical consideration that that boosts performance of Kenyan police-service in Kenya.

The finding that leadership-reform enhances performance of police-service are supported by past empirical studies that effective leadership promotes commitment of followers in their tasks which in return enhances work performance (Djhelilova and Islam, 2019; Eltayeb, Ahmad, Al-Hajri, 2019; Renzi, 2020). The findings are further in line with the institutional theory and reinforcement theory that leadership that is effective is able to coordinate followers' efforts towards effective realization of organization goals. Leaders who coordinate efforts towards the delivery of the set goals are claimed to be effective in delivering set targets (Renzi, 2020). These leaders are able to meet employee's needs, expectations and integrating them with work requirements (Renzi, 2020). By communication and information sharing with followers, leaders are able to promote understanding and learning with regard to performance requirements (Girdwichai and Sriviboon, 2020). Leaders who inspire confidence and trust among followers inculcate a sense of commitment and determination towards performance. (Pinckney, 2015). Therefore, leadership-reform is an important consideration that that boosts performance of Kenyan police-service in regional police headquarters, Eastern Kenya.

Past empirical studies support that police officers who are adequately and appropriately trained are more diligent and effective in their task performance (Kingoo and Njoroge, 2019; Fredrick, 2019; Maina and Waithaka 2017; Kingoo and Njoroge, 2019). Effective training imparts relevant skills, knowledge and attitudes to learners in order to motivate change of behaviors and characters (Benedicta, 2010). In training of police-officers, it helped them to acquire law enforcement skills and helps them to reduce stress responses essential for informed decision making especially during critical incidents (Mumanthi, 2014). Training builds the capacity of officers to diligently perform their task with ease (Kingoo and Njoroge, 2019). Communication skills are claimed to increase positive emotion and vitality in stress management (Andersen and Gustafsberg, 2016; Fredrick, 2019). Therefore, police-training is a critical consideration that that boosts performance of Kenyan police-service in regional police headquarters, Eastern Kenya.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study sought to determine how implementation of police-reform programme (management-reform, structural-reform, leadership-reform, police-training) influences performance of police service in Kenya. Based on the findings, it is concluded that implementation of police-reform programme is a critical factor to consider when designing a strategy for enhancing performance of police-service. Specifically, police-training is concluded to be the greatest contributor to the performance of police service followed by structural-reform, management-reform and leadership-reform in that decreasing order of strength of influence.

Project managers need to ensure that project management processes are reformed well integrated based on the critical drivers of performance. Specific considerations should focus on the capacity needs of project team and stakeholders in order to integrate the needs into the project design and plans. This can be further enhanced through lean organization structures, decentralized management and participatory leadership. The current study demonstrated that improvement in management practices, organization structures, leadership practices and training increases performance of Kenyan police-service. Thus, the government of Kenya can adopt these findings in designing appropriate and relevant reform policies that increase performance of Kenyan police-service.

Suggested Areas for Further Study

Grounded on the limitations of the study, the following studies are suggested:

- i. Moderation of policing policies on successful implementation of police-reform programmes
- ii. Mediation of contextual factors on sustainable delivery of police-reform programmes

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